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Delivering Multicast Traffic in mmWave Systems: Challenges and Performance Analysis

Nadezhda Chukhno^{1,2}, Olga Chukhno^{1,3}, Giuseppe Araniti¹, Antonio Iera⁴,
Antonella Molinaro^{1,5}, Sara Pizzi¹

¹University Mediterranea of Reggio Calabria, Reggio Calabria, Italy

²Universitat Jaume I, Castelló de la Plana, Spain

³Tampere University, Tampere, Finland

⁴University of Calabria, Rende, Italy

⁵Université Paris-Saclay, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

{olga.chukhno, nadezda.chukhno, araniti, antonella.molinaro, sara.pizzi}@unirc.it,
antonio.iera@dimes.unical.it

Abstract

Millimeter wave (mmWave) radio technology is considered as a comprehensive foundation for fifth-generation (5G) networks, which are claimed to efficiently and effectively support both multicast and unicast traffic. One of the main features of mmWave communications is the exploitation of highly directional antennas, at both user and access point sides, that allows providing very-high speed and ultra-low latency services. However, the delivery of multicast traffic in mmWave systems requires special attention because of the nature of the group-oriented services in which receivers simultaneously fed by a single transmission can be located at different positions. The aim of this paper is to discuss the main challenges that must be faced to take advantage of mmWave communication for multicast data delivery. A performance analysis is carried out with the aim to provide a comparison among unicast, sequential multicast, and multicast transmission modes.

Keywords: 5G, mmWave, 802.11ad/ay, Unicast, Multicast

1. Introduction

Recently, millimeter wave (mmWave) wireless networks have become increasingly popular thanks to their capability to cope with the escalation of mobile data demands caused by the unprecedented proliferation of smart devices in upcoming fifth-generation (5G) communication systems [1]. Furthermore, according to both academic and industrial communities, mmWave technology is expected to play a fundamental role even in beyond-5G networks to ensure efficient massive data transmissions [2]. In this regard, mmWaves have been envisaged for a wide range of emerging applications that mainly require the dissemination of a large amount of

data traffic with low latency, such as autonomous driving, mobile video streaming, virtual/augmented/mixed reality (VR/AR/XR) applications, public/road safety, road infotainment, among others. The 3GPP New Radio (NR) technology will exploit the mmWave spectrum to achieve wider bandwidths and higher data rates [3]; a similar approach is used by IEEE 802.11ad/ay families, which will be the focus of this paper.

In this scenario, multicast is a beneficial technique for the improvement of the system bandwidth efficiency. In an IEEE 802.11-based multicast system, a device, which acts as a personal basic service set (PBSS) central point (PCP) or access point (AP), may transmit the same packet to a group of receivers simultaneously, by utilizing the same frequency and modulation and coding scheme (MCS). MmWave transmissions use highly directional antennas to guarantee the gigabit capability and overcome the short propagation range, but they make multicasting more complex to implement in comparison with microwave networks where omnidirectional antennas are typically applied. MmWaves complicate the multicast deployment by posing additional challenges [4], such as beam steering and proper selection of beamwidth. These significant challenges stem from the tiny wavelength and high-frequency band properties of mmWave systems, where the signal is sensitive to rapid channel variations, atmospheric absorption, and severe attenuation. In order to clarify these issues, we investigate the challenges and advantages of mmWave multicast communication in this paper.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, background on IEEE 802.11ad/ay is presented. Section 3 discusses the design challenges of multicast and unicast modes with mmWaves. In Section 4, we describe the system model. Simulation results are given in Section 5, followed by concluding remarks.

2. IEEE 802.11ad/ay specifications

The IEEE 802.11ad/ay standards of the Wi-Fi family operate in the 60 GHz band. The former was ratified in 2012, offering real gigabit data rates. Its successor, IEEE 802.11ay, exploits the same band and provides ultra-high-speed and super low-latency services by introducing advanced physical layer (PHY) features. Furthermore, 802.11ay improved power-saving features make it ideal for wearable devices [5].

2.1. IEEE 802.11ad. The beacon interval structure in IEEE 802.11ad is illustrated in Fig. 1. The Medium Access Control (MAC) design for 802.11ad may utilize both carrier sensing multiple access with collision avoidance (CSMA/CA) and scheduled service periods (SPs) channel access schemes depending on the type of application. In the case of SPs, 802.11ad uses Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), where PBSS PCP utilizes the polling mechanism by asking devices and receiving their feedback. Alternatively, CSMA/CA is used for contention-based

periods (CBP), where devices are allowed to use the same radio channel without pre-coordination with the help of *listen-before-talk* operating procedure. In this work, we consider SPs only.

Fig. 1. IEEE 802.11.ad beacon structure.

The time is divided into beacon intervals (BIs) of total length T ; each BI incorporates: (i) a beacon header interval (BHI), where devices perform initial beamforming which generally involves sectorized antennas (that is, sector-level sweep, SLS), and (ii) the data transmission interval (DTI), including SPs of different connected clients, while containing a beam refinement protocol (BRP) to improve the resulting instantaneous data rate.

More specifically, each BI starts with a beacon time (BT) interval during which the *initiator* transmits sector sweep (I-TXSS) beacons across all M_{SLS} sectors with half-power beamwidth (HPBW) $\theta_{\text{SLS,Tx}} = 2\pi/M_{\text{SLS}}$. The receive sector sweep (RSS) process and feedback during the association beamforming training (A-BFT) announced by the initiator are performed after I-TXSS by the *receiver*. Practically, in A-BFT interval, if more than one client selects the same transmission opportunity (up to eight slots for 802.11ad), the signals collide and devices cannot establish a connection in the current BI.

The receive antenna operates in an omnidirectional mode during SLS and, after measuring the receive signal strength (RSS) across all N_{SLS} sectors, with $\theta_{\text{SLS,Rx}} = 2\pi/N_{\text{SLS}}$, it provides the SLS feedback to the transmitter identifying the sector with maximum RSS value. Based on RSS indicator as well as by using an angle of arrival (AoA), or time difference of arrival (TDoA), the AP can determine the user location information. The training packets are transmitted with the low-power low-rate MCS 0, which provides the reliable communication required to establish the initial beamformed link.

In the announcement time interval (ATI), management information is exchanged between the PCP/AP and the receivers. Once the best sector pair is identified, the

beam refinement phase (BRP) iteratively trains the transmit and receive antenna beams found during the SLS to select a beam pattern pair with finer beamwidths, which are determined by the beam refinement factor b , $b > 1$. Therefore, for the transmit antenna training, both devices sweep through exactly b narrower beams (within the initial transmit sector), while during the receive training, all $M = bM_{\text{SLS}}$ or $N = bN_{\text{SLS}}$ directions should be covered.

To adjust for channel changes, the optional *beam tracking phase* is used during data transmission (DT). Beam tracking is accomplished by appending training (TRN) fields to data packets [6]. More details can be found in [7].

2.2. IEEE 802.11ay. IEEE 802.11ay is an amendment of great interest for applications ranging from high-speed short-range links to wireless backhaul that enable 100 Gbps communications in the unlicensed 60 GHz mmWave band. IEEE 802.11ay incorporates a variety of technical advancements at the PHY over IEEE 802.11ad standard, such as channel bonding and aggregation, single-user (SU) and downlink (DL) multi-user (MU) Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) transmissions, and nonuniform modulation constellation, as well as improved channel access and enhanced beamforming training. For an overview of the IEEE 802.11ay amendment, the reader is referred to [8, 9].

3. Design Challenges of mmWave Multicast and Unicast Modes

3.1. Unicast in Directional Networks. A considerable amount of literature has been published on mmWave communications by focusing on unicast data transmission optimization [10], whereby every user is served independently of the others. The AP sweeps many different beams with minimum beamwidth (to provide high data rate) in the TDMA fashion. The reliability of the transmission is very high since the beamwidth is equal to the resolution and provides the maximum available Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). However, the AP requires a long time to serve all users, as it generates a separate beam for each user to transmit the data sequentially.

3.2. Multicast in Traditional Networks. The multicast concept consists in feeding a group of users by transmitting data packets only once [11]. It consequently improves the bandwidth efficiency compared to unicast mode since all users are served simultaneously by using a single wide transmission beam (omnidirectional), which generally provides very short transmission duration. However, pure multicast schemes are almost infeasible in mmWave systems due to the propagation properties of extremely high frequency (EHF) bands.

3.3. Multicast in Directional Networks. A significant difference between mmWave and traditional networks (e.g., LTE) consists in the use of highly directional transmission beams to cope with high attenuation at EHF bands. We emphasize that mmWave multicast is performed in a sequential manner. Moreover, differently

from conventional omnidirectional networks, the beam orientation and the beam resolution (beamwidth) need to be adjusted in addition to the beam radius.

According to the Friis transmission equation, the received power is directly proportional to the transmitter channel gain, which in turn strongly depends on beam resolution and its orientation. When delivering multicast services in mmWave systems, the following challenges have to be considered [4]:

- 1) Wide beams are more likely to reach all multicast receivers since they can cover a larger angle range and, thus, serve more users simultaneously. However, due to the lower antenna gain that wide beams provide, the supported transmission rate is limited.
- 2) Narrow beams provide higher antenna gain and thus can support higher transmission rates. However, they are limited in coverage in terms of the aperture angle, and may not serve a number of users simultaneously. As a consequence, multiple unicast transmissions are required to reach all multicast users.
- 3) The presence of moving users is more challenging for multicast transmission. In fact, in the case of unicast, the AP is beamformed toward the only receiver, and small movements of the receiver still allow to guarantee a good reception. Differently, in the case of multicast, beams are steered in between users. Hence, some receivers may be close to the edge of the coverage area of a beam.

4. System Model

In this paper, we consider a general public scenario where owners of *wearable devices* are interested in receiving the same content, i.e., the AP transmits data to multiple users through multicast mmWave links. We assume analog beamforming only to analyze the performance of sequential multicast in the TDMA fashion. This means that the AP can transmit through a single beam at a time to serve the users.

4.1. Antenna and Channel Models. In what follows, we assume that devices transmit directionally with the same antenna beam pattern, which is symmetrical w.r.t. the boresight [12]. By this symmetrical assumption, we mean that antennas have a unique beam shape in both elevation and azimuth planes, i.e., their antenna pattern is akin to a conical shape.

In terms of channel model, when the HPBW θ is used, the received signal power at the receiver i is calculated by the Friis equation:

$$P_{\text{rx},i} = \frac{P_{\text{tx}} D_0 \rho(\alpha_i) \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^2 r_i^\kappa}, \quad (1)$$

where P_{tx} is the transmit power, α_i is the current angular deviation of the transmit/receive direction from the antenna boresight for receiver i , $\rho(\alpha_i) \in [0; 1]$ is

a piece-wise linear function that scales the antenna directivity D_0 [12]*, λ is the wavelength, r_i is the separation distance between the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) i , and κ is the path loss exponent.

We assume the Line of Sight (LoS) path only. Hence, the maximum achievable rate D for the multicast group depends on the user with the worst channel conditions and could be estimated according to Shannon's channel capacity as:

$$D = W \log_2 \left(1 + \min_i \left(\frac{P_{\text{rx},i}}{P_{\text{noise}}}, 0 | P_{\text{rx},i} < P_{\text{thr}} \right) \right), \quad (2)$$

where $P_{\text{rx},i}$ incorporates both transmit and receive antenna gains after the BRP phase for link Tx-Rx $_i$, P_{thr} guarantees the minimum required sensitivity threshold for data transmission, W is the bandwidth, P_{noise} is noise power in the channel, which corresponds to $P_{\text{noise}} = W N_0 \text{NF}$, N_0 is the power spectral density of noise per 1 Hz, and NF is the noise figure.

Then, the total duration of data transmission can be found as [13]:

$$T = T_{\text{SLS}} + U(T_{\text{BRP}} + T_{\text{DT}}) + T_0, \quad (3)$$

where $T_{\text{SLS}} + U(T_{\text{BRP}})$ is the overhead on beam training, $T_{\text{DT}} = B/D$ is the data transmission duration, B is the packet size, U is the average number of clients per AP, and T_0 is the total signaling overhead independent on the number of beams.

5. Performance Analysis

In this section, we assess the performance of the multicast transmission in directional mmWave networks via simulations. As a representative scenario, we focus on a group of people in a museum equipped with high-end wearable devices that communicate via the IEEE 802.11ad protocol at 60GHz. We consider resource-hungry applications in a scenario with low or no mobility. We also analyze two patterns of users' distribution: in a line (Fig. 2) and within a sector (Fig. 3). The transmit power is fixed at the level of $P_{\text{tx}} = 23$ dBm, whereas $P_{\text{thr}} = -68$ dBm (MCS 1) [7].

In Fig. 2a, we show results in terms of achievable data rate for multicast, unicast, and sequential multicast schemes when the group of *ten users* is located within a line of length d . We investigate the maximum possible distance d for three considered schemes. As one may observe, the distance d does not affect unicast transmission as each user is served by a separate aligned beam. Regarding the pure multicast, we can see that there is a threshold that determines the maximum angle coverage

* $\rho(\alpha_i) = 1 - \frac{\alpha_i}{\theta}$, if $\alpha_i \leq \theta$, otherwise $\rho(\alpha_i) = 0$; $\rho(\alpha_i) = 1$ corresponds to the antenna boresight in the case of perfect alignment (e.g., unicast transmission after the beamforming procedure). In the case of multicast transmission, each user deviates on angle α from the boresight of the transmitter.

Fig. 2. (a) Data rate and (b) total delay vs. distance d for unicast, multicast, and sequential multicast (with 3 beams).

of the beam. For example, $\text{HPBW}=58^\circ$ provides the larger distance d , whereas narrow beam $\text{HPBW}=4^\circ$ shows the lowest distance d . In Fig. 2b, we present the total data transmission duration T for all three transmission modes. Due to the sequential nature of unicast in mmWave, pure multicast guarantees the shortest data transmission duration. We also emphasize that the beamforming overhead for narrow beams is greater than for wide beams and affects the total transmission delay.

Fig. 3. (a) Aggregated data rate and (b) total transmission duration vs. number of users.

In Fig. 3, we analyze the system performance according to the aggregated data rate (ADR) and the time T required for serving all users for sequential multicast and unicast schemes and evaluate them using a Monte Carlo approach (10^6 simulations). For this purpose, we uniformly distribute users within a sector of 90° of radius

$Rd = 40\text{m}$. The choice of the service area can be explained by the fact that sequential multicast with width $\theta = 58^\circ$ has the smallest number of sequential beams, whereas it can cover the smallest Rd in comparison with more narrow beams. As one may notice, sequential multicast with $\theta = 58^\circ$ guarantees the shortest data transmission duration, hence, the lower delay. However, it provides lower SNR value as well as higher outage probability due to the lower antenna directionality. Using the widest possible beam at EHF bands severely limits the data rate and transmission range. In contrast, narrow beams require a longer data transmission duration. Therefore, we may conclude that the resource management algorithms are of the crucial importance, which dynamically make decisions on the number and resolution of beams in directional multicast by taking into consideration (i) multicast group size, (ii) the shape and size of the service area, (iii) users' locations and density, as well as (iv) QoS requirements. This is of special interest for our future work.

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